

Airtightness Performance Evaluation of the Hyper Tube Transportation System: A Step toward Sustainable and Green Transportation

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Abstract

The hyper tube transportation system demands careful consideration of air resistance, which directly influences energy efficiency and sustainability. This system is emerging as an innovative and environmentally friendly alternative to conventional transport mods, aiming to achieve exceptionally high speed inside the tube structure by maintaining the internal air pressure as low as possible. The applicability of concrete as a construction material for the system needs to be evaluated by considering the effect of potential concrete cracks on the airtightness performance of the system. This study aims to investigate the effect of concrete cracks, developed due to the application of external loads, on the airtightness performance of the concrete tube structure. The study was conducted using an analytical, experimental, and finite element analysis (FEA) approaches. The differential equation was established using an analytical model to predict the internal air pressure change over time in the concrete tube structure. The effect of crack development on the airtightness performance of the system was assessed through the sensitivity analysis, which shows that the development of the cracks is highly sensitive, and the average crack width, in particular, has the greatest impact on the airtightness performance of the system.

An experimental study and FE analysis were conducted by subjecting the concrete tube structure to different stages of displacement at the mid-span of the structure. The results from experimental and FE analysis were used together to establish a damage measure capable of anticipating the degradation of the airtightness performance level of the system. The damage measure was expressed in terms of the volume fraction (V.F) value obtained from FE analysis and can be used effectively for the preliminary airtightness design of the hyper tube transportation system.

Keywords: *airtightness evaluation, hyper-tube transportation, finite element analysis, concrete technology*